

COMPETENCE CHARACTERISTICS OF THE TEACHER OF THE INCLUSIVE PRIMARY SCHOOL

Demchenko I.,

*Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor, Professor of the Department of Social Work and Rehabilitation,
National University of Life and Environmental Sciences of Ukraine
Kyiv, Ukraine*

ORCID ID 0000-0003-4302-7564

Bilan V.

*PhD in Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor at Special and Inclusive Education Department, Pavlo
Tychyna Uman State Pedagogical University.*

ORCID: 0000-0002-6615-5211

ABSTRACT

The article analyzes competitive characteristics of the teacher of primary special school. We defined the main knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for successful work in case of special education. In addition, we proposed hierarchy of competences, which are the basis for renovation of psychological and educational sciences in higher educational pedagogical institutions in the process of training would-be teachers to work with primary school pupils of different level of development, included in general studies in educational institutions.

Keywords: competitive approach, competence, competitive characteristics of the teacher.

Introduction. The modern educational space, due to the reformation of the education system on the basis of humanism and democracy, which requires a review of the requirements for the professional training of specialists. Special attention is paid to the problem of training pedagogical personnel for inclusive educational practice, who in the future will be able to create equal conditions for receiving educational services for all children without exception, regardless of their level of physical, mental, and intellectual development. That is, the higher pedagogical school faces the task of preparing teachers to work with children in the conditions of inclusive education: mastering the professional competencies of working with children in the conditions of inclusive education.

Analysis of recent research. Many studies of Ukrainian and foreign scientists, including I. Bekha, O. Gavrilova, O. Dubaseniuk, O. Semenog, S. Sysoeva, S., have been devoted to the problems of training a modern teacher to perform professional functions in the conditions of educational inclusion, various aspects of the formation of a teacher's professional competence. Tyshchenko, T. Lapanik, A. Markova, V. Slastyonina, J. Raven (J. Raven), I. Hafizullina, V. Khytryuk and others. They are united in that the professional competence of a teacher of an inclusive elementary school must be formed in the conditions of systematic scientific and methodical work, which provides access to the assimilation of a modern array of knowledge about inclusion, is the basis of his continuous professional development and improvement.

Research methods consists in revealing the competence bases of teacher training for work in the conditions of an inclusive educational environment.

Results. Preparing the future teacher to work with students with special educational needs becomes one of the important tasks of higher pedagogical educational institutions and pedagogical education in general. Research shows that future teachers have insufficient training to work with children in an inclusive educational environment. For example, A. Kolupaieva, a

leading scientist in the field of inclusive education, cites in her works data that currently up to 65% of teachers who are students of advanced training courses do not know how to work with children who have special educational needs. Moreover, up to 23% of teachers are unfamiliar with special programs and do not have accurate and in-depth knowledge of the psychophysiological characteristics of children in this category [4]. This confirms the assumption about the insufficient level of preparation of the modern teacher to carry out professional activities in the conditions of inclusive education (misunderstanding of the essence of inclusive education, weak awareness of the personal educational role in the education of children with special needs, low diagnostic culture, outdated psychological and pedagogical methods, etc.). Currently, a new educational paradigm is needed, a new approach to the professional training of the future teacher, based on a competent approach. The term "competence" comes from the Latin "compete" - to meet certain requirements, to be able. The word "competentia" is derived from it, which in Latin means a range of issues in which a person is well-informed, has knowledge and experience [5].

A. Khutorsky, in accordance with this approach, considers competence as an integral formation, which includes a system of theoretical knowledge, practical skills, socially significant and professionally important qualities, acquired experience, the interrelationship of which ensures the effectiveness of the teacher's professional activity, that is, a person's possession of the appropriate competence, which includes its personal relationship to it and to the subject of activity [8, p. 63]. The scientist clarifies that competence is an evaluative and dynamic category that characterizes a person as a subject of activity, reveals his ability to successfully fulfill his powers in one or another professional field. The category "competence" is expressed through such personal qualities as knowledge, skills, values, etc. [8, p. 67]. In domestic scientific literature, the concept of competence mainly includes a certain set of knowledge,

a level of skills and a certain experience in their use. Thus, N. Bibik, L. Vashchenko, O. Lokshina and other domestic researchers consider competence to be a key concept. They point out that, on the one hand, competence organically combines the intellectual and skill components of education, and on the other hand, the ideology of interpreting the content of education formed "from the result" is embedded in the concept of competence [1, p. 87]. R. Gurevich defines competence as a person's ability to apply his knowledge and skills, which is expressed in his readiness to act in specific professional situations. [3, p. 140]. That is, professional competence is considered as an individual's ability to perform professional activities. Moreover, the ability is revealed in the unity of the theoretical and practical readiness of the future teacher. In our study, we will address the professional competence of a teacher of an inclusive educational environment, who must be able to perform various types of activities:

- diagnostic - the ability to make a correct diagnosis of the level of development of the student body, personality development, education and upbringing of individual students, the state of the pedagogical process as a whole and at its individual stages in the conditions of inclusive education;

- prognostic - the ability to predict the results of certain pedagogical actions in the conditions of inclusive education;

- constructive - the ability to construct pedagogical activity in the conditions of inclusive education by setting adequate diagnostic goals (both general and individual) and competently planning one's pedagogical activity, taking into account the various educational needs of students, varying the forms, methods and means of education;

- organizational - the ability to organize pedagogical activity in the conditions of inclusive education, creative application of an individual approach in professional activity (for example, training according to an individual educational route);

- communicative - the ability to establish constructive relations with the subjects of the pedagogical process, which contribute to the effective implementation of inclusive education;

- technological - the ability to implement methods and technologies of inclusive education for children with different levels of development and, in particular, for students with educational needs; - corrective - the ability to adjust the course of the pedagogical process at any of its stages, taking into account the results of intermediate and final diagnostics;

- research - the ability to study, analyze pedagogical phenomena, conduct research and experimental work;

- reflective - the ability to analyze and consciously control the results of one's own activities related to the inclusive educational process.

As we can see, the professional competence of the teacher in the conditions of inclusive education of the institution is an integrative personal formation that determines the ability of teachers to perform professional functions in the process of inclusive education, taking into account the various educational needs of students

and ensuring the inclusion of a child with special needs in the general educational environment of a class, school, creating conditions for development and self-development of all children [7, p.87]. Domestic pedagogy recognizes the importance of the teacher's competence in the joint education of all children as a leading determinant in the course of building an inclusive educational process, while the interpretation of competence comes mainly from an axiological interpretation. Developing it, A. Kolupaieva, defines the professionalism of the teacher in the inclusive class as a resistant and purposeful change in the value attitudes of the teacher regarding the inclusion of children with special needs in the group of peers. This modification is accompanied by a comprehensive rethinking of the teacher's own functional purpose and his role in the process of creating inclusive educational foundations [4]. The further development of this point of view is contained in the views of Russian scientists V. Filimonova and A. Vasylenko, who indicate the existence of a direct correlation between the existential and axiological position of the teacher in the inclusive class and the quality of the implementation of joint learning strategies for all children. The teacher's mood directly affects the general focus of inclusive education, its moral and ethical content and academics [2; 6]. It is necessary to recognize the productivity of the presented position and the significance of the idea of a clear relationship between the emotional and personal characteristics of the teacher and the results achieved during the formation of the readiness of the student with special needs for inclusion in a wider society. It can be assumed that a one-sided account of the axiological bases of the inclusion of children with special needs in the general education school is not the only leading factor in the development of inclusive education strategies, therefore it is advisable to highlight the specific components of the professional competence of the teacher of the inclusive class in the "knowledge - ability - skills" system:

1. Knowledge:

- basics of general pedagogical didactics;
- laws and regularities of the child's development at all stages of his ontogenesis;

- individual socio-psychological features and specifics of the development of special children for each specific category of atypicality;

- compensatory ones replace the mechanisms of functioning and development of the child's body;

- the laws of mental development of an individual in conditions of social deprivation and isolation;

- strategies and tactics of relevant pedagogical interaction with students who have special features in development;

- possible typical reactions of classmates to the specifics of a student with special educational needs;

- functional characteristics and purpose of technologies for tutoring support of a child with special educational needs in an inclusive class;

- socio-pedagogical resources of families of children with special educational needs; - typical processes and phenomena occurring in small groups;

- strategies to prevent professional self-burnout.

2. Skills:

- adequately interact with students with special educational needs;
 - relevantly organize the diagnostic procedure of the socio-pedagogical history of a student with special educational needs;
 - to organize a comfortable psychological and physical environment for learning and raising children with special educational needs;
 - remove egocentric and infantile attitudes from students with special educational needs;
 - eliminate excessive verticalization of communicative relations in the inclusive class;
 - to motivate all subjects of inclusive education for maximum full inclusion of a child with special educational needs in the educational process;
 - to provide competent pedagogical support to children with special educational needs and their parents;
 - implement the principle of a team approach when interacting with various specialists;
 - apply techniques and tactics of uniting the children's team;
 - apply the SWOT analysis method;
 - demonstrate a democratic style of behavior in an inclusive class;
 - quickly respond situationally to problems arising in students with special educational needs and promptly solve them;
 - test in practice the model of cascading education of children with special educational needs;
 - to have methodical methods of adapting the curriculum to the special educational needs of the child;
 - maintain continuity in the dyad "inclusive education
 - further successful life activity";
 - apply preventive measures for the timely elimination of secondary deviations from the norm caused by the isolation and segregation situation of development;
 - to carry out parity contacts with the family of a child with special educational needs.

3. Skills. Skills, in our opinion, should include all the listed skills, which, as a result of repeated repetition, are automatically fixed and become permanent professional actions.

Such a list of knowledge, abilities and skills means that at the university, future teachers must acquire a system of competencies that will enable them to successfully cooperate with children and families in solving emerging problems of inclusive education. The professional competence of a teacher is the presence of a certain stock of knowledge that allows you to act independently when solving pedagogical problems; the ability to apply certain professional pedagogical skills when solving non-standard problems; the unity of theoretical and practical readiness to carry out pedagogical activities; integration of experience, theoretical knowledge and practical skills; the presence of general personality culture, as well as personal qualities significant for the teacher. Considering competence as a complex system formation, it is important to identify its main characteristics: motivational (readiness to demonstrate competence); cognitive (possession of

knowledge of the content of competence); behavioral (experience of demonstrating competence in various standard and non-standard situations); value-meaning (ensuring equal opportunities for all children); emotional-volitional (regulation of the process and result of the manifestation of competence). Competences involve emphasizing not the results of education as the sum of learned information, but the ability of a person to apply it in various problem situations. In the context of our research, it is necessary to identify the key psychological and pedagogical competencies of the teacher in the conditions of inclusive education. Psychological-pedagogical competencies mean internal, potential, hidden psychological-pedagogical neoplasms, which include knowledge, ideas, programs (algorithms) of actions, systems of values and relationships, which allow ensuring the cooperation of children in the conditions of inclusive education, as well as the presence of necessary personality qualities (orientation, activity, willpower, attention to children, kindness, flexibility of thinking, etc.), personal qualities (politeness, attentiveness, kindness, honesty, benevolence, sensitivity, truthfulness, justice, intelligence, emotionality, etc.). In the hierarchy of psychological and pedagogical competencies necessary for a future teacher in working with children and their parents in the conditions of inclusive education, one of the first places is occupied by monitoring competence. It allows you to monitor the process of education and upbringing of children in the conditions of inclusive education and to correlate the actual results with the planned ones, to provide assistance to children with special needs in educational activities and behavior, to cooperate with their parents. The teacher needs to know his pupils, their psychological characteristics, the course of the processes of excitation and inhibition, as well as take into account the peculiarities of the family situation. Pedagogical diagnostics is an integral part of monitoring, it includes control, verification and assessment, accumulation of statistical data, their analysis, detection of dynamics. Diagnostic competence makes it possible to identify the readiness of the future teacher, educator for a valuable relationship with children with special educational needs, establishing contacts with parents, obtaining a sufficient amount of information about families: composition (full, incomplete, large, includes two or three generations of relatives), degree and the nature of the influence of its members on the student, educational level, material well-being, features of family culture, interests and requests of parents, the state of health of the child, to support the process of family education, to establish a relationship with the family of the student in traditional classes and classes with inclusive education; mastering diagnostic tools (questionnaires, tests, conversations, surveys, etc.).

The next important competence of a teacher's professional activity is substantive competence, which is characterized by knowledge of the problems of education and training of schoolchildren, understanding the specifics of the content of inclusive education, acquisition of knowledge and skills of working with children with special needs, limited opportunities. Content competence allows you to structure information related to

children with learning and behavioral problems, the specifics of working with parents, understand the possibilities of one's creative potential, informational and technical support and, of course, the level of preparation of students and their characteristics. Mastering prognostic competence by the future teacher, educator allows to predict the development of their activities, the problems of working with children with special needs, with their parents, to develop models of their decisions and to predict the consequences of applied decisions. Prognostic competence allows the future teacher to plan his future activities, determine the meaning of life, form a valuable attitude towards education and a healthy lifestyle, and have appropriate value orientations. This is an important guideline in educational work. Design competence is a leading component of a teacher's professional competence. It is considered as one of the main results of the specialist's professional and pedagogical training and ensures the readiness of the teacher to work in the conditions of inclusive education, cooperation with parents. Design competence includes the teacher's ability to predict the results of his activity, to determine the sequence of his actions when achieving the goal, that is, to combine pedagogical strategy and tactics. Reflective competence is related to the future teacher's ability to evaluate his work as a whole, the ability to see cause-and-effect relationships between his tasks, goals, methods, means, conditions, and results. Reflective competence is a process of awareness, analysis, critical understanding by the subject of the pedagogical process, how his actions and deeds, methods of managing the educational process are perceived by those who study, contribute to the realization of the tasks of education and upbringing. It is focused on the teacher's understanding of the process and results of his activities with children and parents, during which evaluation and reevaluation of his knowledge, abilities, mistakes and opportunities take place. Communicative competence characterizes the features of the future teacher's communicative activity, the specifics of his communication with students in the process of inclusive education, and their parents. It allows you to organize a verbal and non-verbal exchange of information, as well as to diagnose the personal properties and qualities of the interlocutor; the ability to develop strategies, tactics and techniques of interaction with children and their parents, to organize their joint activities to achieve certain socially significant goals; the ability to identify oneself with the interlocutor, understand how he is perceived by the communication partner and empathize with him. The teacher is a leader of changes in education and works in the conditions of changes: increasing the amount of scientific-methodical and research components in the structure of pedagogical activity, inclusion in the creation of new models of pedagogical practice and their scientific understanding. A significant direction in the development of research competence is the development of the teacher's ability for self-analysis and project activity. The teacher's research competence can be defined as the ability and readiness of an individual to independently and effectively perform research activities, predict their results and apply them in practice in the

conditions of inclusive education. Research activity allows you to expand the set of skills and abilities necessary in professional activity, because it is a means of developing intellectual skills, which, in turn, to some extent ensure the success of any activity, in particular, in the field of inclusive education and family upbringing. The presence of research skills or research competence is a way to solve any task of professional pedagogical activity. Competencies related to technologies and methods of working with children in the conditions of inclusive education, with mastering the skills and abilities of working with children who have problems, are of particular importance. It is important that a teacher at a university master the system of working with students who need help. Therefore, in order to implement the competence approach in the conditions of inclusive education, it is necessary for the teacher to have certain knowledge, abilities, skills and personal qualities that would allow him to successfully carry out educational work with schoolchildren.

Conclusions and prospects. The proposed hierarchy of competencies necessary for the effective work of a teacher in the conditions of inclusive education and their implementation in the educational process of a higher school will allow to increase the quality of training of future teachers. The purposeful implementation of the competence approach in the process of professional activity will contribute to the mastery of future teachers in the methods and forms of work in the multi-level student body of the primary school and their parents.

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